

A Framework for University Social Responsibility and Sustainability: The Case of South Valley University, Egypt

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Abstract—The environmental, cultural, social, and technological changes have led higher education institutes to question their traditional roles. Many declarations and frameworks highlight the importance of fulfilling social responsibility of higher education institutes. The study aims at developing a framework of university social responsibility and sustainability (USR&S) with focus on South Valley University (SVU) as a case study of Egyptian Universities. The study used meetings with 12 vice deans of community services and environmental affairs on social responsibility and environmental issues. The proposed framework integrates social responsibility with strategic management through the establishment and maintenance of the vision, mission, values, goals and management systems; elaboration of policies; provision of actions; evaluation of services and development of social collaboration with stakeholders to meet current and future needs of the community and environment. The framework links between different stakeholders internally and externally using communication and reporting tools. The results show that SVU integrates social responsibility and sustainability in its strategic plans. It has policies and actions however fragmented and lack of appropriate structure and budgeting. The proposed framework could be valuable for researchers and decision makers of the Egyptian Universities. The study proposed recommendations and highlighted building on the results and conducting future research.

Keywords—Corporate social responsibility (CSR), South Valley University, Sustainable University, university social responsibility and sustainability (USR&S).

I. INTRODUCTION

WE live in a global world and an increasingly competitive environment. The challenges facing higher education include internal and external factors. From one side, internal factors include the “tensions between research and teaching structures” [13], the inability of dealing with the growth of number of students entering higher education institutes especially in developing countries such as Egypt, the resistance to change from the employees and staff members, and the centralization of governance of higher education institutes. On the other side, the world conference of higher education held by the UNISCO highlighted that the modern university is facing substantial change as a result of two central trends in external environment. These trends are “acceleration in the pace of change itself and the globalization of the economy and of technology” [36] causing challenges

for higher education institutes. External factors include: 1) the growth of the world student number and demand on higher education institutes services [19] causing the change into internationalization [3], [40]; 2) the adoption of "corporatization" in the higher education system [29]; 3) the lack of public funds available for higher education [14], [3], causing organizational failure [29], [40]; and 4) "the continuous development of Information and Communication Technology, ICT, innovation and development of technologies" [38]. The Magna Charta Universitatum Observatory concluded in different publications the need for changing the Universities role, academic freedom, and sustainability [43]. External changes have led to different results: 1) Vallaey's [24] mentioned that society makes demands on universities and academic institutions to be more involved with social issues, to align between their goals and social expectations and needs [27], [40], [10], and to increase their roles in social progress especially in developing countries [20]; 2) involvement and intervention of external stakeholder in internal issues of higher education and research; and 3) changes of students' expectations and demands regarding university educational services [14]. This research is an effort to build on the previous research focused on USR models and practices of higher education institutes, and provide a new framework for USR&S. It will evaluate the current situation of SVU's social responsibility and sustainability SR&S. Practically, the framework provides a base for the development of the role of universities and could help university's leaders to evaluate and develop the university policies and practices toward both community and environment.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR)

The development of the concept of CSR started in the 1970s with the concept of corporate social responsiveness, CSR [8] then other definitions emerged in the 1980s such as “CSP [Corporate Social Performance], public policy, business ethics, and stakeholder theory/management” [5]. The idea behind CSP is the recognition that firms do have ethical responsibilities and that they must also respond reasonably to the needs of society [8]. McWilliams and Siegel [26] show that stakeholder's theory identified a wide range of stakeholders that organizations must respond to their needs instead of focusing only on the needs of shareholders. They

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concluded that there is some level of CSR that will maximize profits which is the interest of shareholders meanwhile will satisfy the needs of other stakeholders for CSR.

According to the Green Paper, "CSR is a concept whereby companies integrate social and environmental concern in their business operations and in their interaction with their stakeholders on a voluntary basis." [9] Gaberman [15] stated that "CSR consists of the voluntary activities of a company, often at the risk of short-term adverse effects on profitability, but with the expectation of enhanced long-term shareholder value". However both definitions could be criticized when it comes to the voluntary practices. Vallaey [37] suggests that responsibility means accountability, however because there is no obligation to keep what organizations promise, social responsibility is about "declarations of good intentions, which can easily turn out to be no more than bluster". Another common definition of CSR is that of the World Business Council for Sustainable Development, stating that "Corporate social responsibility is the continuing commitment by business to behave ethically and contribute to economic development while improving the quality of life of the workforce and their families as well as of the local community and society at large" [41].

Two dimensions of CSR need discussion, theory and practice. First is theory of CSR. Vallaey [37] argued that there is a lack of theoretical agreement about social responsibility and the theory behind it and how to be socially responsible. Researchers developed different models of CSR. Dodd [45] argued that corporate managers have economic responsibilities toward stockholders, to achieve profit, and social responsibilities to society. He suggested that "business is permitted and encouraged by the law primarily because it is of service to the community rather than because it is a source of profit to its owners". Carroll [6] developed the pyramid of responsibilities with economic responsibilities at the base, philanthropy at the top and legal and ethical responsibilities in between. Others used the concept of corporate social performance and developed a typology that divides the outcomes of CSP into policies, programs, and impacts based on three levels of analysis institutional, organizational, and individual [44]. Steg et al. [28] proposed a typology identifying three impacts of the firm, "economic, social, and environmental performances". Second are the practices of CSR. Universal principles of CSR started to be generalized by integrating guidelines to be reported by organizations globally. Different organizations worldwide report routinely based on "The Global Reporting Initiative formed in 1997" in areas of "economic, environmental and social performance" [15]. Moving from reporting to standardization, International Organization for Standardization (ISO) expects that socially responsible organizations should contribute to three sustainable developments, economic growth, social development, and environmental protection and suggests developing international social responsibility standards based on the needs and concerns of developing countries [18].

B. University Social Responsibility and Sustainability

The previous discussion shows that researchers focus on studying CSR from a business organization's perspective. Hence a key question to answer is: what is the relevance of social responsibility and sustainability to universities which can be termed as USR&S? In 2009 the University Social Responsibility Alliance held the first University Social Responsibility International conference to discuss and explain the new concept of USR to all interested universities [30]. Reiser [46] defines the USR concept as "a policy of ethical quality of the performance of the university community (students, faculty, and administrative employees) via the responsible management of the educational, cognitive, labor and environmental impacts produced by the University, in an interactive dialogue with society to promote a Sustainable Human Development". Some researchers [38] argue that it is hard to agree on the definition of USR and suggested that USR includes different issues, "... the need to strengthen civic commitment and active citizenship, ... volunteering, ... an ethical approach, developing a sense of civil citizenship by encouraging the students, the academic staff to provide social services to their local community or to promote ecological, environmental commitment for local and global sustainable development". From the above discussion we can suggest that USR is the accountability of establishing and maintaining an ethical approach of the management of university's internal and external stakeholders, strengthening societal citizenship and commitment to society and providing services to local community, and encouraging environmental commitment and sustainable development.

Researchers proposed different models of USR. Reiser [46] identified four types of impact that USR might have: "Organizational impact" which mean that University has a social and environmental responsibility toward employees and environment, "cognitive impact" which relates to knowledge as University has scientific and technical responsibility of the research activities, "social impact" through the increase of "communities of mutual learning towards social development" and "educational impact" through the students preparation and development to be responsible citizens and ability to participate in development of society. Dima et al. [12] proposed a model of social responsibility in universities of Romanian and identified six dimensions of USR which are: "Alumni-oriented projects, Inter-university cooperation, University-high-school Cooperation, University-business Cooperation, International cooperation and Socio-cultural and ecological projects". From a practical point of view, some researchers [2] studied the view of ten public relations practitioners on the need for universities to carry out CSR programs in Nigerian universities. They concluded that universities with socially responsibility to their stakeholders can improve on their image and suggested that to be socially responsive, universities need to pay attention to six issues, "economic responsibility, philanthropic responsibility, environmental responsibility, employee wellness and health, employment of qualified lecturers and legal responsibility" [2]. Other researchers [11] found that Istanbul Bilgi University

has CSR practices, but with a minimal extent with focus on teaching CSR. In practice, many universities adopted the concept of USR by signing the "Magna Charta Universitatum" to solve the economic, environmental, and social problems of the society. It has become the base for universities' values and actions in issues related to social responsibility specially university autonomy and academic freedom of different actors and decision makers, staff, researchers and students [23].

Velazquez et al. [39] define sustainable university as "a higher educational institution, as a whole or as a part, that addresses, involves and promotes, on a regional or a global level, the minimization of negative environmental, economic, societal, and health effects generated in the use of their resources in order to fulfill its functions of teaching, research, outreach and partnership, and stewardship in ways to help society make the transition to sustainable lifestyle". Another definition [7] shows that a sustainable campus community is "the one that acts upon its local and global responsibilities to protect and enhance the health and wellbeing of humans and ecosystems. It actively engages the knowledge of the university community to address the ecological and social challenges that we face now and in the future".

The environmental role of universities has become an issue of global concern for university researchers, policy makers and planners as a result of the realization of the impacts of activities and operations of universities on the environment and the role of universities in the sustainable development of society and environment.

Some researchers [25] focus on the concept of sustainability in University campus practices organizationally and technically. They suggested that "for a university campus to be sustainable, it must preserve the environment, stimulate economic growth, and improve the well-being of the surrounding community and society" [25]. Different initiatives and declarations published in this regard. In 1990, over 300 university presidents and chancellors in over 40 countries have signed the 'Talloires Declaration' an action plan for incorporating sustainability and environmental literacy in teaching, research, operations and outreach at colleges and universities [35]. The Halifax Declaration provided an action plan based on short and long-term goals for Canadian universities and identified specific frameworks for action within the university [17]. The United Nations Conference on Environment and Development held in Rio de Janeiro, 1992, chapter 36, identified a lack of environmental awareness throughout the world and all countries argued to increase public awareness involvement and training and promote sustainable development education [34]. Based on Swansea Declaration [32], participants of 400 of the Association of Commonwealth Universities focused on finding ways by which universities might engage and respond to challenges related to solving people problems and the environment through sustainable practices. The International Association of Universities, IAU, urged its members universities to establish and disseminate a clear understanding of sustainable development, to understand environmental risks facing the planet earth, to teach and conduct research based on

sustainable development needs of the society, to search for practical measures to achieve sustainable development, to review their own operations to reflect best sustainable development practices and finally to integrate and implement the ways and means of this declaration in the mission of each of its members [22]. 'The University Charter for Sustainable Development' is another instrument established by 'Copernicus Charter' to express commitment of many universities in environmental issues and focus on co-ordination to mobilize the resources of higher education institutions to be leaders in making sustainable societies and stress the need for changing the concept of environmental values within the higher education community [33]. The Thessaloniki declaration in 1997, based on the UNESCO Conference of Environment and Society, Education and Public Awareness for Sustainability, in Greece, argued a radical social change for environmental change [42].

Many universities created individual institutional policies and employed programs to achieve campus sustainability such as ISO 14001 and the European Eco-Management and Audit Scheme (EMAS) and green building initiative [42]. However some researchers [21], [25] see that ISO 14001 is not multidimensional since it only provides environmental sides of sustainability and lack attention to economic or social dimensions. Common Principles of Sustainability in institutional policies and declarations suggested different priorities and principles for sustainability in higher education mainly listed by [42] as "moral obligations, sustainable physical operations, encouraging sustainable research, public outreach, inter-university cooperation, partnership with government, NGOs and industry, develop interdisciplinary curriculum and ecological literacy". Some researchers [21] examined the implementation of social responsibility in the University of Colorado Boulder and found that the university has implemented many aspects of sustainability including issues related to (research, student activities, facilities management) however it has faced some challenges affecting achieving integration and coordination inside campus. They suggested that university sustainability initiatives could be in one of the four stages named: "grassroots...; executive acceptance of the business case for sustainability...; the visionary campus leader...; and fully self-actualized and integrated campus community". Each stage has some evidence of different implementations regarding sustainability of university [21].

Literature review shows that researchers give little attention to the social responsibility practices of Arab countries' Universities. One study [1] discussed how Hashemite University achieves development, sustainability, and competitiveness through applying USR. It suggests that applying social responsibility in Hashemite University could ensure development and sustainability for the university and society. We can conclude that much research conducted focusing on the social responsibility and sustainability of higher education institutes specially universities in developed countries. Many universities and declarations adopted principles of social responsibility and sustainability. However

there is a lack of research in this issue in developing countries specially Egypt. Since there is no one model for social responsibility and sustainability of university, the concept of USR needs more development and integration to the concept of sustainability.

III. RESEARCH PROBLEM

This research provides a framework of university social and environmental responsibility from a multidiscipline view and a strategic management orientation. It explores the mission, vision, values, plans, policies, structures and practices of social responsibility of SVU toward community and environment.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The case study approach is suitable in qualitative research as an interpretative tool [4]. Focusing on a single university case will help to investigate easier current policies and practices of USR&S. SVU was chosen and interviews conducted with Vice Deans of Community Services and Environmental Affairs representing 12 faculties to collect data using open-ended questions. The researcher learning, teaching and training experience for more than 25 years in SVU and his experience as the director of Quality Assurance Center for three years, helped in tracking and observing the USR&S policies and practices. The university's strategic plan, web site, organizational structure and reports, were used to collect appropriate secondary data.

V. A FRAMEWORK FOR UNIVERSITY SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND SUSTAINABILITY

The following is a proposed model of the framework of USR&S (Fig. 1). It integrates social responsibility into strategic management and identifies the vision, mission and values to guide all other three dimensions, management, policies and actions, and evaluation.

Fig. 1 A proposed framework of USR&S

The framework integrates the three parts of the Egyptian universities' activities and services known as education,

research and community services and environmental affairs. To manage social responsibility and environmental orientation of university, the framework integrates management, policies and actions and evaluation together to assure association between various functions of the university and integrate both internal and external stakeholders in the framework. The framework intends to maintain a multi-dimensional approach to USR&S and assure synergy between all faculties and SVU's community service and environmental affair sector that govern the practices of USR&S. The framework links between different stakeholders internally and externally using communication and reporting tools.

VI. EXPLORING THE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY AND SUSTAINABILITY OF SVU

Based on the proposed framework, USR&S can be operationally defined as a multidimensional approach that includes the establishment and maintenance of the vision, mission, values, goals and management systems; elaboration of policies; provision of actions; evaluation of services and development of the social collaboration with stakeholders to meet current and future needs of the community and environment. To be socially responsible, SVU need not only to fulfill legal and structural requirements, but also to invest in human capital, the environment and the relations with different internal and external stakeholders. The next part will focus on discussing and investigating the different dimensions of the proposed framework with application on SVU.

A. Management of USR: Integrating Social Responsibility into Strategic Planning

Vision, Mission and Values: The vision of SVU is "scientific leadership to build a knowledge society and sustainable development" [31]. We can infer that integrating the role of university on building a knowledge society and sustainable development represents a legitimate and moral foundation.

Fig. 2 Values of SVU, Adopted from [31]

From one hand the public standing of SVU rests fundamentally on the execution of its social purpose, to serve society by providing socially needed services and solve the economic and social problems of the society. On the other hand, SVU has a moral purpose integrated in its culture values

of serving society needs.

SVU focuses on elevating and monitoring high level of ethical performance in all its operations in order to build comprehensive relationships with all stakeholder groups based on trust. SVU adopts a mission statement, where it states its purpose, core values, and responsibilities and guide objectives towards its stakeholders. It states that: "SVU provides education based on the needs of society; conducts creative applied research through providing an excellent learning and educational environment to prepare qualified graduates based on quality standards and to support scientific research; and creates an effective partnership to meet the aspirations of community" [31]. This mission governs all objectives of the strategic plan. It can be inferred that the mission focuses on the social role of the university based on the main three dimensions of university functions: education, research and community services and environmental affairs, as shown in Fig. 1 of the proposed framework.

The role of the mission statement is to conceptualize the USR and link all structures and people together. Although the University has 20 institutes, only 12 have strategic plans and integrated social responsibility into their mission statements in

accordance with the university strategic plan and mission statement. The core values that govern the organizational behavior can be summarized in Fig. 2. These values are published in the website of the university and communicated with employees through quality assurance workshops conducted in faculties to establish quality assurance systems, develop strategic plans and establish rules of conduct to assure commitment toward society in all activities of the University. SVU communicates its values with students through involving them in activities and projects to assure quality standards and train them on conducting research and serving community. The university center of staff and leaders development plays another role in communication of the university values through training and development of staff members and managers of SVU. Other stakeholders, such as universities, business community, governmental and non-governmental organizations are communicated through the university portal, partnership initiatives and conferences. The university has developed and adopted an Ethical Code of Conduct of different activities. It communicates and monitors it in all faculties and institutes.

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Fig. 3 A stakeholders' analysis of SVU

SVU's Stakeholders Analysis: To understand the University's stakeholders' needs and fulfill these needs, SVU should first identify these stakeholders. An analysis of the university in relation to internal and external stakeholders reveals the suggested structure (see Fig. 3) of the university three campuses, its faculties, special units and centers and facilities that can serve different stakeholders.

Goals and Objectives: Relevant goals and objectives are set for SVU to support university social responsibility. These goals link teaching, research, community service and environmental affair dimensions with focus on internal and external stakeholders and protection of environment. These goals are [31] 1) To establish educational and learning environment based on scientific research and encourage students to build their competencies and prepare qualified graduates who are able to adapt to the needs of the labor market, SVU aims at achieving teaching and learning excellence by raising the quality of teaching and learning and apply for accreditation of academic programs of the university's institutes. 2) To improve and develop scientific research, SVU facilitates the task of scientific research and development and integrates them dynamically so that applied research has its applications to develop southern provinces of Egypt in all areas. 3) To build effective partnerships with local community, SVU aims at co-operating with the local community to develop Upper-Egypt area and protect the environment. 4) To develop the institutional capacity of the university and improve its infrastructure, SVU aims at having institutional accreditation of the university and its faculties. The following part explores issues related to plans, structure and budgeting and stakeholder analysis of USR in SVU.

USR Action Plans: SVU adopted action plans to achieve the goals and objectives related to its social responsibility. There is an annual plan for community service and environmental affair of SVU. Each faculty and institute should establish its own plan of community service and environmental affair in conjunction with the university strategic plan. Although most of the faculties and institutes have their own action plan related to its social responsibility, not all of them fully implemented these plans because of the lack of appropriate organizational structure and fund.

Structure of USR: Studying the current structure of SVU shows that of the 20 faculties and institutes only 12 have vice deans of community service and environmental affairs. The University Council of Community Service and Environmental Affairs handle responsibilities and powers as set by the Law of Universities' Regulations of Egypt. The council includes three members that represent three stakeholders of community with experience background. This is an indication of the involvement of external stakeholders in planning and execution of plans of USR&S.

Budgeting USR: Social and environmental plans of SVU lack adequate funds to implement social responsibility and solve environmental issues in campus. External stakeholders support and special funds of the university are mainly the sources of the current budget of community service and

environmental affairs. Hence it is important to increase the budget of the sector to be able to implement the strategic plan of the university. Fund raising is suggested as a source of finance of SVU.

B. Policies and Actions

Work place and services for internal stakeholders: By law, policies in workplace ensure adequate actions against all forms of discrimination, both in the workplace and at the time of recruitment. SVU's faculties and institutions stress ethical behavior in all stakeholder transactions and interactions. Highly ethical conduct has been adopted and monitored in action. SVU provides accommodation and health services to ensure welfare and sufficient protection of faculty members, employees and students in campus and encourage social interaction. Accommodations for single faculty members and demonstrators are provided in low cost. The university provided accommodation for 5309 students in the academic year 2013/2014 and 4100 students in 2014/2015. The University current safety practices focus on fire-fighting within the campus through training courses for faculty and staff members. Health services for faculty and staff members and students using University hospitals. Regarding welfare of faculty, staff and students, the University offers activities through sporting centers, staff and faculty members clubs and associations, student unions and youth welfare departments and cafeterias. Still there are many issues areas of development such as quality of accommodation services, building conditions in heating and air conditioning especially in classrooms and study halls and using social and meetings rooms inside the workplace to encourage social interactions between staff, faculty members and students.

Research issues: Although some research focus on issues related to various disciplines in the area of environment and social issues, there is a lack of connection between University and external stakeholders in industry and business sectors. SVU sought to improve the performance of faculty members, assistants, and the system of scientific research by signing agreements with the universities from USA, Japan, South Korea, Germany, Italy, Sudan, Malaysia and others, enabling the University to follow the scientific progress in various places of the world and the exchange of researchers and co-operate with international universities and funding bodies in research projects. South Valley Knowledge Transfer center (SV-KTC) is one of twelve centers for Knowledge Transfer in North African universities to maintain co-operation between EU and the universities in Middle East countries. The center is established to support the University and Industry co-operation to encourage innovation and implementation of new technology. Technology Innovation Commercialization Office TICO is another project with co-operation with Academy of Scientific Research and Technology of Egypt. However the impact of research and projects on industries is not clear. The weakness of research in Egypt in general is the lack of implementation to solve economic, industrial and social problems.

Education issues: SVU focuses on delivering high-

quality education to community of large geographic area in Egypt, including three governorates Qena, Luxor and Red Sea. It has 20 faculties and institutes in different fields of medicine, nursing, oral and dental medicine, veterinary medicine, commerce, arts, fine arts, education, specific education, law, engineering, archaeology and science. The University has achieved a good academic record where 36739 undergraduate students joined its faculties and institutes in 2014/2015 academic year, representing both male and female students, a good indicator of its societal and educational role. Most of Faculties provide higher education programs. The current number (2014/15) of Doctoral degree students are 120, Master degree students are 605 and Diploma degree students are 10595. However the number of students differs from one Faculty to another one. The high number of students studying Diploma is due to demand on the faculty of education. Open Learning Centre of SVU provides learning to community in the field of archaeology, arts, law and commerce. The number of students graduated in 2014 was 2360 and number of students enrolled in all levels until in 2015 is 4379. SVU's Faculties need to add some courses in their education programs to address topics related to social responsibility and sustainability such as sustainable development, environmental management, Nile and sea protection, sustainable agriculture, social justice, green building construction and recycling industries.

Community services and environmental issues: To raise the level of the environmental awareness inside and outside campuses, SVU organizes symposiums, conferences, and workshops and provides service convoys and awareness campaigns in the fields of agriculture, medicine and veterinary medicine. It holds a yearly environmental week in March every year. Regionally, it provides workshops and organizes conferences about the environmental issues such as the one discussed the environmental problems in Arab countries held in October 2010. It organizes a yearly international conference of environment.

In the field of using sustainable energy, SVU started using some units of solar water heating to supply hot water and reduce electricity consumption. SVU waste management and environment protection efforts focuses on reducing solid waste and recycle trash of the University campus to produce useful products to the University using the recycling factory in campus. In the field of health protection, the University applies a no smoking campus policy in and outside buildings.

SVU provides consulting services in different fields. In discovering and studying natural resources in Upper Egypt, it can help in the industrial and economic development of the region especially in Marble and Granite Industry, solar energy and water resources. In business fields, SVU provides economic, business management training and consulting to industrial and service sectors of business and governmental organizations. The central laboratory provides services to researchers and University students and community in photography, chemical and biological analysis of drinking water, waste water and industrial wastes. Fitness Center qualified many of the sportive injuries, trained the special

needs students on weightlifting games and performed sportive competitions. The Faculty of Agriculture is responsible for the farms and grows different crops like wheat for the University bakery and vegetables for catering services or selling inside the University.

IT project established the infrastructure of IT and porter of the University and linked the University with the supreme council of the Egyptian Universities. It provides electronic mail and web services to all faculty members, staff and students to help in the educational, research and social services. It also provides training and ICDL license.

Other services include teaching and training foreign Languages by German, English and Spanish Centers. SVU works in collaboration with Arab and foreign universities and hosts them in the cultural, artistic, sportive and religious festivals it holds. University guest houses in Cairo, Red Sea, and Qena provide accommodation for staff members and employees with cheap price. University hospitals provide health services for all staff members, employees, students and citizens. Clinics, labs and internal units provide medical services free of charges or with minimum costs.

The Career Development Center of SVU is an important center for the development of competencies of students and new graduates to be involved in the job market. It provided training to 2060 trainees in the fields of career development such as entrepreneurship, English language, communication skills and CV writing. The ICT Center provides training to students, employees and staff members in the field of Information and Communication Technology such as Microsoft Office, Internet Literacy, Windows, Networks and SPSS. The Pathway to Higher Education is another project that provides training of soft skills, English Language, entrepreneurship and training of trainers for both students and graduates of the University. The number of trainees in this project since establishment until 2015 is 18451 students.

SVU needs to enhance policies and actions in reducing University and environmental impact in issues such as [16] using green energy, reducing energy and water consumption, safe waste water treatment and usage, pollution prevention, and protection of the natural environment. Other environmental issues include using sustainable transportation options in campuses and buildings code to adapt with natural environment especially hot weather of Upper Egypt.

C. Monitoring and Evaluation of Impacts

For SVU to be socially responsible, it must provide transparent information on the results that it has obtained in economic, social and environmental areas of interests identifying the public confidence. The current methods used in SVU are quarterly reports about all types of activities that are gathered in a yearly report provided to the board of the University and disseminated to the University's Faculties and Institutes. However, evaluation methods need to be based on quantitative and qualitative approaches using surveys and meetings to collect data from all the relevant people and departments about the level of services and satisfaction of different stakeholders inside and outside the University. These

data need to be analyzed to evaluate the social responsibility and role of the University toward environment and reports need to be provided based on these results.

D. Communication

The communication process will help in raising awareness across the University's stakeholders. As a result the concept of social responsibility and sustainability is gradually spread through the University and community. SVU has its own self-reporting method of the implemented plans, by evaluation of the plans not evaluation of the impact of the plans. Hence, SVU can benefit from the IT center and Quality Assurance Center to evaluate the impacts of policies and plans on community, environment and the University reputation. Communication with different stakeholders is important in evaluation and reporting using different media such as website, annual reports, leaflets, conferences and workshops.

VII. CONCLUSION

Understanding the changing environment of higher education institutes and involvement in this change can reshape the role of universities and gain reputation and competitive advantage. Egyptian Universities need to continually rethink, question and reform their role to society promoting social co-operation and cohesion and change values and practices toward environment.

Different models of USR found in the literature, however this study proposed a new USR&S framework integrating social responsibility with strategic management through the establishment and maintenance of the vision, mission, values, goals and management systems; elaboration of policies; provision of actions; evaluation of services; and development of social collaboration with stakeholders to meet current and future needs of the community and environment. The framework links between different stakeholders internally and externally using communication and reporting tools.

The study shows that SVU integrates social responsibility and sustainability in its strategic plans. It has policies and actions however fragmented and lack of appropriate structure and budgeting. The proposed framework could be valuable for decision makers of SVU; however it requires establishing policies and providing actions inside and outside campus. It needs to integrate multidimensional approach that focuses on co-operation and involvement of different stakeholders of the University.

Although SVU increasingly recognizes its social responsibility role to internal stakeholders, community and environment, it has yet to adopt a clear framework to manage practices. It has to integrate these practices in day-to-day management involving key stakeholders based on a strategic vision, mission and action plans. Managers and employees need development and training in order to acquire the necessary skills and competencies. Students need to be aware of the University social responsibility, to learn their role and to acquire the necessary skills to engage in job market and develop community. Hence SVU needs to integrate social responsibility and environment issues in the curriculum of

different faculties.

Universities can help to adopt social responsibility practices by disseminating best practices. They require effective transparency about universities' social and environmental performance. University administrators and other stakeholders internally and externally can play an important role in areas such as work conditions and environment. They can identify, support, and strengthen their key stakeholders and prompt University to adopt socially responsible practices fulfilling their needs.

Managing USR&S requires the use of appropriate measures and human resources for these measures. Because SVU is interested in mechanisms to apply quality standards based on the Egyptian National Association of Quality Assurance and Accreditation of Education, NAQAAE, framework, the results of this study could help SVU to develop an important dimension which is University social services and deal with different external stakeholders hence fostering the implementation of quality standards. It is recommended that SVU establish a council for USR&S on the level of University and another one on the level of faculties that has representatives from each administrative and academic area and involves members from external stakeholders. The number of staff working in the Community Service and Environmental Affairs need to be increased and job descriptions need to be designed in accordance. Increasing the budget to run activities of social responsibilities is very important if the University wants to be leading in this field.

VIII. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

There is a methodological criticism of the case study approach because of its limitation of external validity to provide generalization of findings which can be applied to all universities. Hence future research can use a representative sample of managers, staff, faculty members, students and other external stakeholders to study and gain better understanding of SVU approach to USR&S or expand the results of the study and compare between different Egyptian universities using a quantitative approach. Researchers could study the factors affecting the adoptions of social responsibility and environmental policies and practices such as leadership styles and organizational culture. Other research could measure the impact of the adoption of social responsibility on community development.

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